

Partnership and Cooperation of Technical Vocational Education and Training College Internship Programme for Mainstreaming Youth Transition into Employment

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This article analyses how partnerships between Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) colleges, Sector Education and Training Authorities (SETAs) and employers contribute to effective internship that support the transition of young people into employment, using Ekurhuleni as a case study. A combination of the Theory of Change, the Transactional Partnership Model and the logic model was used to make sense of how inputs, activities and institutional arrangements mediate internship outcomes. A qualitative design was used with nine semi-structured interviews conducted with key informants. A thematic analysis was used to interpret the data. The findings suggest that partnerships are foundational for internships as they provide a structure for the other elements of effective internships and for interns' placement opportunities. Partnerships also help align curricula with workplace practices, mobilise resources, and support employability. But these benefits are diluted by the absence of formalised frameworks. We located the limitations of partnerships in the context of unproblematised market-led and human-capital approaches to TVET, which often reduce the purpose of education to employability. This has the potential to undermine holistic development and to entrench neoliberal and colonial legacies. To counter this, a capability approach, which advocates for holistic human development, emerges as a better alternative. Using the findings, a six-pillar internship model, with partnership development as a key pillar, was proposed to improve internship effectiveness. The model is aimed at guiding colleges and partners to design effective internship programmes that can support skills development and the social justice agenda in South Africa.

Keywords: Technical vocational education and training (TVET) college, internship, partnerships, Ekurhuleni

This paper investigates partnerships as a mechanism to capacitate public TVET institutions to support the transition of the youth into work through effective internships. It is guided by this question: To what extent do partnerships contribute to the effectiveness of TVET internships? It draws from research conducted in Ekurhuleni TVET institutions and their partners to investigate the effectiveness of TVET internships as a mechanism to enhance employability. Ekurhuleni is one of the regions with high youth unemployment and a high concentration of TVET colleges. The research used qualitative approaches, conducting semi-structured interviews with key informants from the TVET colleges and partners selected using purposive sampling. The paper starts by providing a brief background to contextualise the discussions. This is followed by a literature review on partnership and TVET internships scholarship,

and a theoretical framework to create a lens for presenting and discussing the research findings, which follow immediately after the methodology discussion. The paper concludes by discussing implications, providing recommendations, and proposing a model to improve the effectiveness of TVET internships, which places the role of partnerships at the centre.

Background

The technical and vocational education and training (TVET) institutions in South Africa are intended to contribute to building a capable state through providing skills, which are core to reducing unemployment, poverty, and inequalities (DHET, 2013; Needham, 2019). However, limited resources and limited capacity, partly caused by underfunding, undermine the ability of public TVET institutions to contribute optimally to these goals (Allais, 2025; Anthonie, 2019). Given this and the rising global youth unemployment, partnerships between TVET colleges, industries and other relevant stakeholders are often positioned as one of the catalytic strategies that could enhance the efficacy of TVET through improved governance and access to resources, to enable support for internships among others. However, the effectiveness of partnerships as a support mechanism for TVET is curtailed by weak partnerships with stakeholders, inadequate policy frameworks, poor institutional arrangements, and lack of national norms and standards to guide internships outside the public sector (Njengele et al., 2024; Papier, 2017; Notsi, 2024).

The global youth unemployment crisis, estimated at 64.9 million unemployed youth worldwide (ILO, 2024) necessitates robust and

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evidence-based interventions. In regions like Sub-Saharan Africa, the unemployment crisis is even more severe with 3 in 4 youths not in secure employment (ILO, 2024). Even more pronounced is youth unemployment in South Africa with about 7,1 million youths (15 & 35 years) unemployed out of an estimated 13 million unemployed people (StatsSA, 2025). The limited ability of the education system to adequately prepare the youth for transitioning into work exacerbates the situation (Tan et al., 2023; Arfo, 2015; Notsi, 2024). The severity and the urgency of youth unemployment have prompted both the global and South African policy agenda to prioritise employability (Singh & Ehlers, 2020; Njengele et al., 2024) as part of the state's socio-economic mandate.

TVET partnerships and internships are acknowledged as important areas of scholarship (e.g., Hora et al., 2019; O'Higgins & Pinedo, 2018; Kapareliotis et al., 2019). However, in South Africa, research on these areas, especially in relation to the role of partnerships in supporting TVET internships governance, is scant and patchy (Papier, 2017; Mesuwini et al., 2023). The paper contributes to the literature in these areas and to policy and practical discussions on how partnerships could capacitate TVET colleges to enhance their contribution to employability through internships.

Review of Literature

TVET plays a key role in enhancing employability through integrating theoretical and practical learning (Kattiyapornpong & Almeida, 2022; Badawi & Drăgoicea, 2023). Internships are at the centre of integrating theoretical and practical learning, which makes them critical in TVET's ability to produce skilled and employable youths (World Bank, UNESCO & ILO, 2023). However, some scholars point to weak partnerships with industries as one of the hamstrings to effective internships, while others point out that TVET colleges do not adequately prepare students for the world of work (Papier, 2017; Tan et al., 2023; Arfo, 2015). These observations are among the reasons TVET colleges and policy makers look to partnerships as one of the possible ways of supporting the colleges' capacity to support internships. The positive role of partnerships in supporting TVET internships as an instrument for mainstreaming youth into employment is supported by various studies (e.g., McDonald, 2020; O'Higgins & Pinedo, 2018; Hora et al., 2019; Rose, 2020). The following section discusses TVET in South Africa, internships and employability, and partnerships for context and as key concepts for this paper.

Overview of TVET in South Africa

TVET is distinguished from other forms of formal education by its focus on technical and practical skills to support employability and respond to skills shortages (Badawi & Drăgoicea, 2023). Skills shortages in South Africa are documented in the DHET's annual scarce skills report, the 2024 IITPSA ICT Skills Survey, and the 2023/2024 Annual Critical Skills Survey (EXPATWEB, 2024; IITPSA, 2024) among others. The EXPATWEB report, for example, indicates that local companies struggle to recruit, among others, professionals in engineering (23%) and ICT (14%) Artisans. TVET supported by partnerships and reinforced by internships, is among the mechanisms to respond to the skills shortages in South Africa (Needham, 2019; Republic of South Africa, 2013) and to deal with socio-economic challenges such as poverty, unemployment and inequalities.

TVET Colleges are governed by the Department of Higher

Education and Training (DHET) and through institutional councils, which are composed of various stakeholders. Among the stakeholders in councils are donors who, in many cases are also partners to the colleges. The direct governance by the DHET at the national level is indicative that TVET is treated as an important national priority (Arfo, 2015). The following policies provide a governing and legal framework for TVET: the Continuing Education and Training Act 16 of 2006 and its amendments, including the Further Education and Training Colleges Amendment Acts of 2012 and 2013; the Skills Development Act 97 of 1998 as amended, National Skills Development Strategy, and the National Qualifications Framework Act 67 of 2008. The strategic objectives of TVET and its articulation with other education levels are expressed in the White Paper for Post-School Education and Training (2013). Notably, internship policy outside the public sector is non-existent, meaning that there are no norms and standards guiding internships. This could lead to disparities in internship outcomes and consequently to unequal access to the labour market.

TVET institutions are relatively easy to access, which makes them a viable alternative to improving the labour market chances for youths from lower socio-economic backgrounds (Anthonie, 2019). However, TVET colleges are often associated with low status and stigmatised as institutions for the academically less capable, which results in graduates discriminated against. Consequently, it is difficult for TVET institutions to attract talent and/or to be taken seriously as an alternative to other forms of higher education (Arfo, 2015). Underfunding for the institutions does not make the situation any better.

Integrating internship into the TVET qualifications is not only intended to deal with skills shortages, but also to improve the quality of the qualifications through practical skills. The integration involves completing equal periods in colleges for theoretical studies and in an internship programme. It is important to have an understanding of how partnerships could support internships effectiveness.

While the positive role of TVET is acknowledged (e.g., DHET, 2013; Badawi & Drăgoicea, 2023) its neoliberal framing is critiqued for its narrow focus on the needs of the markets and for potentially minimising the public good part of education, which is critical for holistic development of students (Ngewangu, 2021; Vally & Motala, 2014; Powell, 2014). Furthermore, the policy discourse pays little attention to the decolonisation of TVET, which is necessary, given that some of the challenges facing the sector, like rigid and outdated curriculum, and poor integration with industries can be traced back to the sector's colonial legacy (Anthonie, 2019; Quan-Baffour & Akpey-Mensah, 2022; Needham, 2019). The need for decolonisation and contextual factors shaping TVET dictates that more research and theorising work should be done outside the Western frames of reference to shape the sector to respond appropriately to local peculiarities and challenges (Anthonie, 2019; Rose, 2020).

Internships and Employability

Internship and employability are closely related, given that an internship is conceptually understood as a mechanism to improve employability. Drawing from various scholars, we define internship as a planned and structured way of preparing the youth to transition into work through experiential learning, taking place in the real work environment, and guided by experienced mentors, for the purpose of

enhancing the interns' employability (Hora et al., 2019; Afeti, 2018; Kapareliotis et al., 2019; Igret et al., 2022; Mabiza et al., 2017). Employability is defined as “technical or non-technical competence attributes and one's traits that can increase his or her employment potential and also enable them to successfully perform desirable job requirements” (Mello et al., 2017; cited in Ndlovu & Van Wyk, 2023, p. 130). So, the point of an internship is to equip interns with technical and non-technical attributes to increase their chances in the labour market. A correlation between internship and employability has been established in previous studies (e.g., Jackson & Bridgstock, 2021; O'Higgins & Pinedo, 2018; Hora et al., 2019; Silva et al., 2016; Robert & Saar, 2012), meaning that internships do enhance employability.

Effective internships are underpinned by interlinked and complementary factors such as institutional arrangements, partnerships with industries and other relevant stakeholders, well-structured partnerships, and quality mentorship supported by meaningful tasks (Zehr, 2016; Tomlinson et al., 2017; Notsi, 2024). To increase the chances of internship programmes succeeding, these factors should be taken into account when conceptualising and implementing the programmes. Institutional arrangements clarify the structures required to execute the internship programme, rules, and roles and responsibilities of those tasked with executing the programme. Well-structured internships, on the other hand, eliminate arbitrariness by stating the objectives, the resources required and the intended outcomes of the programme, while complementing the institutional arrangements. Minimising arbitrariness reduces the likelihood of an internship programme being misaligned with the intended outcomes and/or being ineffective. Good quality mentorships increase the likelihood of positive internship outcomes as they provide interns with intellectual, practical, psycho and social support (McHugh, 2017; Alawamleh & Mahadin, 2022). While these factors complement each other, we focus on partneologicalrship partly because the other factors pivot around a strong partnership and partly because of the focus of this paper.

Partnerships

Partnerships are purpose-driven, voluntary 'multifaceted interactions' between organisations to find innovative ways of maximising the use of resources and expertise for the mutual benefit of the partners - and by extension society (Copenhagen Centre, 1999; cited in Seddon & Billett, 2004; Frølund et al., 2018). In the context of TVET internships, mutual benefits of partnerships include, but are not limited to, alleviating the shortage of internship placement opportunities, broadening access to resources, better integration of theoretical learning and practice (Njengele et al., 2024; Richards & Spanjaard, 2025) and, by extension, improved understanding of the theoretical knowledge by students (Karapeliotis et al., 2019). Ultimately, a combination of these components enhances youth transitioning into employment, thereby supporting the state's interventions (Richards & Spanjaard, 2025; Mesuwini et al., 2023; Muzari, 2023; Notsi, 2024). Industries benefit from partnerships as primary consumers of TVET outputs in the form of research and employable graduates.

However, the downside is that the neoliberal assumptions underpinning TVET partnership and internship discourses privilege markets in their framing. This could weaken the quality of graduates by depriving them holistic education that encompasses important

elements like citizenship education and decoloniality. Holistic education is necessary for skills such as critical thinking and entrepreneurship, which diversify opportunities for the TVET graduates. TVET curriculum should go beyond merely serving the markets and unwittingly reinforcing a colonial worldview by overemphasising a narrow conception of employability. Human existence is more complex and multifaceted to be reduced to finding employment as the primary “if not exclusive, source of meanings and measure of value for human beings” (Anderson, 2003; Cited in Powell, 2014: 11). To counter these potential unproductive assumptions driven by human capital theory, some scholars (e.g., Quan-Baffour & Akpey-Mensah, 2022; Powell, 2014) advocate for human capability approaches, which is based on Sen (2001) work that emphasises holistic approach to human development, underpinned by the strive for justice than by the needs of the markets.

There is also a problematic assumption that TVET students' pathways to transitioning to the labour market are straightforward or as Kruss and Wildschut (2016) put it, 'assumes linearity of transition', as often implied in these economic employability discourses and official policy. They assume a 'black box' logic where students are put in the 'black box' from one end and then expected to come out on the other end employable, which is not how human reality, characterised by unpredictability, works (Cook, 2022; Hora et al., 2019). So, narrow approaches to TVET may not be helpful in framing and improving transition to employment (Kruss & Wildschut, 2016). Nonetheless, the benefits of partnerships, discussed in detail below, should be acknowledged.

Internship Placement Opportunities

Increased and diversified internship placement opportunities fortify TVET colleges' ability to contribute to reducing unemployment and poverty through skills development. In South Africa, internship placement opportunities are also important because the TVET qualifications require students to complete half the duration of the course in an internship, without which the students cannot complete their qualification. Limited internship placement opportunities have resulted in some students not completing their qualifications, which has implications for skills development and supply (Sishi, 2022). Ekurhuleni institutions that participated in the study placed 69% of students in internships (Notsi, 2024) while the remaining students had to find internships through other means, which could be difficult for students without the necessary social and cultural capital. These capitals include social networks, the language, and particular dispositions. While internships have many benefits, they could also reproduce inequalities because they tend to be classist by privileging students with relevant cultural capital (Tomlinson et al., 2017; Klein & Weiss, 2011). Studies suggest that relationships with industries are crucial to alleviate limited placement opportunities (e.g., Muzari, 2023; Fei et al., 2020; McDonald, 2020). McDonald (2020) argues that without industry partnerships providing a structural base, implementation of internship programmes would be almost impossible. Internship placements are recognised as central to TVET outcomes, such that other countries invest in them. In Taiwan, for example, internship placements are formalised and coordinated by the Taiwan Experience Education Program (TEEP), meaning that they are not left to chance, as is to some extent in South Africa (Taiwan Experience Education Program, 2015-2025).

Internship placements provide platforms for experiential learning, which colleges cannot. Furthermore, partnerships with

certain industries provide opportunities for interns to access cultural capital that enhances their employability, which capital cannot be found in the colleges and is unique to those industries (Jackson et al., 2005; cited in Klein & Weiss, 2011). This is crucial for increasing opportunities for students who may not be able to access such capital without the help of college partnerships. Partnership also has the potential to add value to curricula and pedagogy, which are crucial for shaping the nature and scope of internships (Richards & Spanjaard, 2025) as discussed below.

Skills Requirements and Curriculum Enhancement

Public TVET colleges and industry partnerships create platforms to negotiate and articulate the parties' expectations. These include resources required, the nature of the curriculum and pedagogy, and practical training required to meet the skills expectations. The expectations also shape the internships' focus and their envisaged outcomes (Singh & Tolessa, 2019). Limited interaction between industries and TVET colleges tends to limit the possibility of exchanging ideas between TVET institutions and industries about skills required by industries (Papier, 2017). Systemic and institutional huddles such as highly centralised curriculum design and weak coordination of partnerships contribute to the gap between skills produced by colleges and skills needed by industries, limiting TVET colleges' ability to meet their skills mandate (Quan-Baffour & Akpey-Mensah, 2022; Singh & Tolessa, 2019). This defeats the purpose of reducing unemployment and providing relevant skills. To minimise the mismatch between the skills produced by colleges and those required by industries, partnerships provide a platform where employers can enrich the curriculum by advising on long-term skills requirements (Scott & Willison, 2021).

Partnerships are also crucial because they facilitate the exchange of knowledge on current development in workspaces and in research (Marinho et al., 2020). Such exchanges have the potential to enhance curriculum, pedagogy, and experiential training, which in turn enhances employability. Partnership pedagogy, which is the incorporation of knowledge and practices found in industries into the curriculum, teaching, and assessment, to bridge the gap between theory and practice, is important for producing relevant skills (Richards & Spanjaard, 2025). Industries can also play a critical role in the assessment of students' practical skills, given their wealth of knowledge (Njengele et al., 2024). Intentional and properly crafted partnership can enhance the integration of academic learning and the needs of the industries (Richards & Spanjaard, 2025; McLachlan & Pretti, 2018). Furthermore, given the central role played by TVET lecturers in preparing the students for work, partnerships could play a crucial role in facilitating work-integrated learning placements for lecturers (Mesuwini et al., 2023). Many TVET lecturers in South Africa are underqualified (one in five lecturers lacks the requisite workplace practical skills) (Mesuwini et al., 2023). Partnership could provide opportunities for self-improvement and for keeping lecturers' knowledge current in line with industry developments and trends, which ultimately improve learning and teaching, and by extension transitioning into employment (DHET, 2013).

Broadening access to Resources

Partnerships facilitate access to necessary resources such as finances, technologies, machinery, and expertise, which contribute to the capacity of the TVET institutions (Muzari, 2023; Frølund, et al., 2018; Singh & Tolessa, 2019) to enhance students' practical

learning and their employability. Service partners such as SETAs, for example, not only provide internship placement opportunities and funding for other institutions' internship programmes, but they also facilitate links between employers and colleges (DHET, 2013; Notsi, 2004). SETAs also fund and conduct work readiness training and induction workshops to prepare students for participation in internships (Notsi, 2024). Other partners, such as civil society organisations, provide career counselling among other services (Papier, 2017). Access to the latest technologies and machinery, which industries are likely to have, could also enhance learning and keep the students' knowledge current. All these inputs are likely to enhance students' transition into work.

However, the benefits of partnerships are not automatic; they require formalised and purposeful agreements (HRDC, 2014). But TVET colleges often lack clearly defined partnership frameworks, which weakens their ability to take advantage of the benefits partnerships offer. Emphasising the need for purposeful partnerships, the Transactional Partnership model postulates that partnerships must be goal-oriented to be effective, a point which is reinforced by HRDC (2014) advocating for clearly defined partnerships with specified common goal (s). Supporting these views, Frølund et al. (2018) argue that to derive maximum benefits from partnerships, strategic goals for the partnerships and their modalities should precede partnership agreements. This will guide the selection of relevant partners and guide how partnerships should be conducted. Partners should also agree on key performance areas as a basis for accountability and for evaluating the successes and weaknesses of the partnership (Frølund et al., 2018; HRDC, 2014).

However, even partnerships with clear goals and clear operational modalities have complications caused by, among others, different organisational cultures, bureaucratic systems and approaches, monetary interests, reliability of partners, and in some cases different understandings of the envisaged mutual outcomes (Thompson & Jesiek, 2017). These could cause contradictions and potentially overshadow the mutual interests between the partners. Too much centralisation of partnerships could also cause bureaucratic complications, negatively affecting the agility and functioning of partnerships (Frølund et al., 2018).

This literature review identified a range of factors that contribute to the success of TVET internships, chief among them being partnerships. However, the interaction of these components as part of a complex system of governance with implications on internships as a mechanism to enhance employability and transitioning to work remain under-theorised. We draw from the Theory of Change, the Logic Model, and the Transactional Partnership Model to provide a theoretical base to explain the complex interaction between the elements. This will also assist to frame the discussions to better understand the inputs required, assumptions made, and relational dynamics underpinning partnerships. In turn, they enable us to explain how the endeavours of the state to develop skills for employability are enabled or constrained by the TVET systems.

Theoretical Framework

A combination of the change theory, transactional partnership model, and the logical model created a lens to understanding the role of partnership and their modalities. To fortify the lens of analysis, previous research findings and theories on internships are brought together with the models. At a fundamental level Transactional Partnership Model is centred around the idea that partnerships are by

their very nature transactional, and that being the case, it is important to clearly articulate the nature of the transaction. This minimise the chances of failure. Clarity on goals and the nature of the transaction, is consistent with points made earlier (HRDC, 2014).

The logic model on the other hand is “a graphical/textual representation of how a programme is intended to work and links outcomes with processes and the theoretical assumptions of the programme” (Hayes et al., 2011: 1-2). This means that to have an effective partnership, all the inputs and the sequence of events should be understood and articulated properly. The value of this is that the model will assist the potential partners to assess the inputs required from each of them and at what point they are required. This could help them to clarify their roles in the partnership, which is likely to strengthen the partnership. The theory of change is about understanding how an intervention like partnerships can result in desired change. It further postulates that an understanding of the underlying theory of a programme is the basis for understanding how the programme works and whether it works or not (De Silva et al., 2014). It makes the underlying rationale of a project explicit, which supports planning, implementation, and assessment of the project (Reinholz & Andrews, 2020). In other words, it explains why partnerships are necessary as an intervention to bring change and how they can be implemented and monitored. Combined, the theories/models provide an understanding of why partnerships are necessary, what should be their purpose, and what practical steps and inputs are required to implement them. This theoretical lens helped to frame the interview guide such that it focuses on key inputs, output and processes.

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework to Connect Theory, TVET/Industry Partnerships, Internships, and Building State Capacity

Note. Source: Authors' conceptualisation using Theory of Change, Logical Model, and the Transactional Partnership Model

The conceptual framework illustrates the interconnectedness between theory, endogenous and exogenous factors that shape partnerships. This graphical depiction is a summary of our lens. Next, we now present the research methodology used for this research paper.

Method

Whilst the original research employed mixed methods, we only use the qualitative component of the data to align with the focus of this paper - the role of partnerships in supporting effective internships. Primary data was collected through in-depth interviews with key

informants from seven (7) SETAs and two (2) TVET colleges, selected using purposive sampling. In total, nine (9) semi-structured interviews were conducted and then transcribed. Manual and iterative coding was used, guided by the key dimensions underpinning the Transactional Partnering Model, like mutuality of partnerships, clarifying of roles and responsibilities, and clearly articulated goals.

These in-depth interviews enabled the researcher to pose probing questions while maintaining topic focus, discovering new insights, and evaluating partnerships from various viewpoints. Additionally, reviewing literature relevant to TVET education, internship programmes, youth mainstreaming, and transitions work provide a context. To interpret and make scholarly sense of data generated from the respondents, a theoretical framework was adopted for the study, and in this instance, the Theory of Change, Transactional Partnering Model and the logical model were used to provide a framework to assess partnerships as a key contributing factor towards effective internships at TVET colleges.

Thematic analysis was employed to analyse and interpret data, facilitating the creation of comprehensive descriptions, in-depth explanations, and the identification of themes supported by the data (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019). Ethical considerations were also addressed by obtaining a research clearance from North-West University, and permission from the TVET colleges and their partners. We also obtained informed consent, ensured participants' confidentiality and anonymity through written undertakings and through signing consent forms.

Results and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the research findings to assess the extent to which partnerships contribute to effective TVET internships. Using a combination of the Transactional Partnership Model, the Theory of Change, and the Logical Framework Model as a lens to provide a framework of understanding partnerships as a supportive mechanism (inputs & processes) and their role in TVET internships outcomes. The findings are based on thematic analysis of the semi-structured interviews with key informants. The analysis is anchored by themes that emerged from the interviews and literature review, such as partnerships as structural necessity for internship placement, as platform to access resources, as contributors to the curriculum, and as contributors to employability outcomes. The discussion locates the findings in the context of high youth unemployment, limited institutional capacity to support internships, and skills shortages, while showing the central role played by partnerships in integrating the various inputs to address these challenges.

Partnerships as Structural Necessity for Effective Internships

The participants consistently pointed out that partnerships are structurally necessary for internship placement opportunities, expanding access to resources to support other elements of effective internships, and to ensure that experiential learning is conducted in the real work context. As two of the participants put it:

“We have seen a marked improvement in the skill levels of our students, thanks to the practical training provided by our industry partners” (Participant 4).

“The collaboration between our college and external companies

has significantly increased the employment rate of our graduates” (Participant 3).

This finding suggests that without some form of agreement with other stakeholders, implementing internships would be a big challenge. In line with the Theory of Change, which explains the rationale behind putting a structure or an intervention to achieve certain outcomes, the findings provide the rationale for partnerships as a necessary intervention. While the logic model assists to locate partnerships as a foundation in the internship value chain. This is consistent with previous studies that emphasises the structural centrality of partnerships in providing experiential learning platforms for application of theoretical knowledge (e.g., Marinho et al., 2020; Richards & Spanjaard, 2025; Karapeliotis et al., 2019; Afeti, 2018; Fei, Waheeb, & Sulaiman, 2020). McDonald (2020), for example, argues that the implementation of effective internships would be very difficult, if not impossible, without the support of a partnership. However, Jackson and Bridgstock (2021) caution that while partnerships facilitate access to internships, the access is mediated by external factors such as social and cultural capital and student agency, which means that access is not necessarily equal. The structural necessity of partnership in internships is also in concord with the Transactional Partnership Model, which postulates that there is a need for partnerships founded on a clear value proposition while defining the roles and responsibilities of the partners. The integrating role played by partnerships is supporting the capacitating of TVET colleges and, consequently, the state's ability to execute its socio-economic mandate.

The Importance of Partnerships for Curriculum Support

The study results affirm that service partners' involvement is crucial for the success of internship programmes as they provide resources, internship positions, and practical experience that academics cannot offer. The respondents highlighted the importance of partnerships and the role played by partners as per the below quotes:

“Industry partnerships are essential for keeping our curriculum relevant and ensuring our students are job-ready upon graduation” (Participant 5).

“Partnerships with industry have been instrumental in providing our students with the hands-on experience they need to transition smoothly into the workforce” (Participant 1).

These responses allude to the important roles played by service partners in transitioning students from school to work. Secondly, improving technical skills that also serve as a contributing factor towards preparing students to transition to work. Allais and Wedekind (2020) argue that educational institutions and industry collaborate on training courses to meet labour market demands. Support for literature suggests that service partners are essential to TVET programme success. These links must be maintained and reinforced to enable TVET graduates to find jobs.

The assertions made by the respondents are consistent with previous findings, which affirm institutional-level partnerships as an important component of successful internships (e.g., Afeti, 2018; Fei, Waheeb, & Sulaiman, 2020; Fleming, McLachlan, & Pretti, 2018) which suggests the need for strong ties between education providers and industry stakeholders to strengthen vocational training programmes. Furthermore, data show that strategic partnerships, as reflected in the stairway model, foster strategic

allocation of resources and support (Baken, 2008) which may enhance the effectiveness of internships.

These findings are in concord with the Transactional Partnering (TP) model, which emphasises the value of partnerships, especially if they are underpinned by clearly defined objectives. Amongst the internship-to-employment transition best practices is the role of partnerships as articulated in the literature (HRDC, 2014). Furthermore, partnerships should be informed by value proposition, rather than partnership for partnership's sake (HRDC, 2014; Makgato & Moila, 2019; Fleming et al., 2018).

Qualification to Work Transition

The findings illustrated that establishing effective partnerships in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) internships facilitates the transition of students into the workforce, providing them with essential skills and experiences that can lead to meaningful employment opportunities or even pathways to self-employment. Furthermore, these collaborative efforts not only enhance the practical training aspects of the curriculum but also contribute to students' overall academic fulfillment as they gain real-world knowledge and hands-on experience that align with their educational objectives. The study respondents emphasised these impacts as follows:

“The qualification rate has improved, and the absorption rate by companies has increased” (Participant 2).

“Several interns have successfully transitioned into full-time employment after completing their internships” (Participant 3).

The quotes above demonstrate that if strategic partnerships are established, impactful results can be achieved. While Jackson and Bridgstock (2021) emphasise co-curriculars' impact on graduate employability, they also assert that the outcomes of internships are mediated by access to social and cultural capital, recruitment bias, labour market demands, and geographic location, which suggests that the outcomes may be classist and varied for different students. These scholars support the idea that TVET programmes need strong collaboration. This is also consistent with Di Meglio et al. (2022) argument that industry interactions boost graduate employability. Corroborating this is Germany's successful internship system that has led to low youth unemployment rates and a highly skilled workforce (Busemeyer & Trampusch, 2012).

Challenges in Partner Engagement

The study findings highlighted that while partnerships are crucial for supporting transitioning through internships, there are challenges and complexities that come with seeking and participating in partnerships. The participants cited partner selection, unpredictability of partner contributions, and inconsistency in support as some of the major obstacles. Some of the challenges are highlighted in the following responses:

“Securing reliable partners who can consistently provide quality internships is a major challenge we face” (Participant 6).

“The inconsistency in partner contributions often leads to disparities in the training and support our students receive” (Participant 2).

Inconsistencies in partnerships have the potential to undermine the effectiveness of internships and access to employment opportunities, as they cause unequal student skill development and preparation for employment. These challenges have been noted in

previous studies, like Silva et al. (2018) who suggest that uncertainty in partnerships may impair internship programme performance. While Wolfgram and Ahrens (2022) suggest that difficulties in finding reliable partners impact student success. The Transactional Partnering Model suggests that inconsistency in partnerships may compound the challenges faced by partners, such as differing interests, understanding of nature of the partnership, and expected outcomes (Thompson & Jesiek, 2017). This research highlights the importance of partner reliability and engagement. Less effective and unequal internships outcomes attributed to inconsistent partnerships have broader implications for the developmental agenda.

Synthesising the Findings of the Study

The study found that effective collaboration among TVET institutions, various industries, and Sector Education and Training Authorities (SETAs) is essential for capacitating TVET institutions. Such collaborations not only enhance the quality and practical training aspects of these internships but also ensure that graduates acquire relevant skills and experiences that align closely with industry demands. This strategic approach significantly enhances the employability of TVET graduates, better equipping them for successful careers in their respective fields. Third, the findings pointed to challenges in establishing reliable and beneficial partnerships due to inconsistencies and conflicting interests among partners. This challenge, if not resolved from the onset, may hinder the effectiveness of the internship, thus hindering the success of students in gaining employability skills.

The Model

Based on the findings of the original study, a model was proposed for designing and implementing a robust internship programme in the context of Ekurhuleni TVET colleges. The model emphasises that effective internships are supported by several key pillars that complement each other to ensure the success of the programmes. Development of strong and purposeful partnership stands out among these pillars as they not only broaden access to resources to support internships, but they are structurally necessary for the operationalisation of internships by enabling the other pillars such as programme design, curriculum relevance, mentorship and monitoring and evaluation. Below, we provide a summary of the other pillars before we discuss partnership development in detail.

Key pillars for supporting effective internships

Institutional Arrangements: putting in place policies and procedures, a structure for governance, and the appointment of personnel with clear key performance areas to implement the programme, is key to effective internships.

Programme Design: Carefully designed internship programme minimises arbitrariness and ensures alignment between the programme and its goals. Aligned programmes and goals contribute to the integration of theory with practical learning.

Programme Preparation: Preparing both the student and the internship host before the programme commences is important, which includes ensuring the internship support mechanisms are in place, and that students and internship hosts understand what is expected from them. This pillar and the next one are closely related and overlapping.

Internship Implementation: Implementation involves recruitment of interns based on a clear recruitment policy, and providing orientation about protocols, terms and conditions of their internship including

processes and procedures. Allocating the interns' actual tasks that are aligned with the intended outcomes of the programme. To achieve this, communication between the college, the students and the internship host must be clear.

Monitoring, Evaluation and Support: Constantly monitoring and evaluating internship programmes is crucial for tracking progress, addressing challenges, providing lessons and improving the programme.

Partnership Development

Partnership development is the sixth pillar of the model, emphasising that strong and strategic partnerships are fundamental to effective internships. These partnerships provide a robust framework that supports various aspects of the internship programme, including securing resources, ensuring curriculum relevance, and offering mentorship opportunities. By fostering collaborations between TVET colleges and industry stakeholders, internships can better align with real-world demands, thus equipping students with the necessary skills and experiences for their future careers. This pillar is also seen as a prerequisite in the overall success of TVET internships due to the fact that without partners, students cannot complete their qualifications and gain practical skills, which will subsequently affect their transition to work.

Partnership Negotiations and Partner Agreements

Effective negotiations are crucial in establishing clear, mutually beneficial agreements between the TVET colleges and potential partners. These negotiations should focus on defining the roles and responsibilities of each party, ensuring alignment with the programme's goals, and securing the necessary resources and support. Successful negotiations need to be formalised through agreements such as MOUs, MOAs or SLAs. Formalised agreements should be comprehensive, detailing elements such as the scope of the partnership, commitments of each party, and the metrics for measuring success, and consider all legalities and adherence to policies and regulations to safeguard partnership's integrity. These elements, which are in line with the Transactional Partnering Model's assertion that partnerships should have clear and mutually beneficial purpose (Sameroff & Mackenzie, 2003) are crucial to build strong, strategic partnerships that can support effective implementation and operationalisation of internship programmes in TVET colleges.

Implications of the Study

Theoretical Implications: The study contributed to enhancing theoretical understanding through a review of the literature and through interrogating the key concepts applicable to partnerships and internship programmes. The application of the Change Theory, Transactional Partnering Model and the Logical Model contributed to theoretical discourse in that it brought forth a different lens of understanding partnerships as a key pillar to useful internships. The study also highlighted the fact that internship as a discourse is linked to productivist discourses underpinned by human capital theory. The inclusion of capabilities theory mitigates the narrow lens provided by human capital theory.

Methodological Implications: The use of a qualitative approach provided a way of looking at complex relationships between different variables. Methodology discourse could be enriched by evaluating the use of mixed methods to study internships as opposed

to applying either quantitative or qualitative approaches. Perhaps other studies could employ this methodology as it proved to be rigorous.

Policy Implications: The study contributes to understanding how strong partnership mediates the outcomes of internships, therefore contributing to policy debates on how effectively connect internships with the broader skills development agenda. Secondly, the policy disparity between public service internships and private sector internships, lacks specific national policies, was highlighted. Further research and policy debate are needed to find ways of closing the existing policy gap.

Practical Implications: the study illuminated the key ingredients that contribute to the efficacy of the internship programme. These include functional partnerships, quality mentorship, integration of theory and practice, and supportive institutional arrangements. Bringing together these elements, a model to guide the practical implementation of internship programmes was proposed. This model has the potential to assist college internship units and industries in improving conceptualisation, design and implementation of internships.

Recommendations

To strengthen partnerships and collaboration efforts to support effective TVET internships, we recommend the following:

Partnership Framework: Developing a robust partnership framework that outlines an approach to partnerships including the expectations, responsibilities, and benefits for all parties involved. Clear guidelines are important for managing relationships and ensure that all stakeholders are aligned with the programme's objectives, and establish mutual benefits.

Dedicated Personnel for Relationship Building: Assigning dedicated personnel to focus on relationship building by maintaining ongoing communication with partners, addressing any issues that might arise, and ensuring that the partnerships remain mutually beneficial.

Clear Outcomes: Setting clear outcomes for the internship programme, which are measurable and aligned with the goals of both partners. This will ensure that all parties have a common understanding of the objectives of the partnership, creating a frame of reference for continuous improvement.

Encouraging More Partners: It is essential to find ways to attract additional partners to support the diversification of partnerships to offer more placements and diversified experiences for interns, and enhance their employability.

Critical Approach to TVET Internships and Partnerships: TVET Internships and partnerships, the neoliberal framing should be critically engaged to develop contextualised and holistic approaches.

Conclusion

The study affirmed the significance of well-defined partnerships in supporting the mainstreaming of the youth into work through supporting internships. This reinforces the importance of building strong partnerships and creating a structured, supportive environment for interns. It also pointed to the challenges of establishing, maintaining, and implementing partnerships. It problematises partnerships by pointing uncritical neo-liberal conceptualisation, which leaves blind spots, like prioritising holistic development of students and the need for decolonisation. With

respect to research, further investigation into best practices for partnership building and the impact of internships on long-term employment outcomes is recommended.

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